

Photolytic Chlorination of Aromatic Nitro Disulphides

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Photolytic chlorination of bis(2-nitrophenyl) disulphide (Ia), bis(2, 4-dinitrophenyl) disulphide (Ib) and bis(4-nitrophenyl) disulphide (Ic) in carbontetrachloride resulted in the formation of the corresponding nitrobenzenesulphenyl chloride (IIa-c) in good yields. bis(3-nitrophenyl) disulphide (Id) under these conditions did not afford the corresponding sulphenyl chloride. Ia and Ib on photolytic chlorination in aqueous acetic acid afforded 2-aminobenzenesulphonic acid (Va) and 2-amino-4-nitrobenzenesulphonic acid (Vb) respectively. Ic under these conditions gave 4-nitrobenzenesulphonic acid (VI).

DISULPHIDES are known to dissociate homolytically at elevated temperature and under photolytic conditions¹⁻³. The ability of an *ortho*-nitro group to transfer its oxygen(s) to an adjacent group under photochemical conditions is known and has been reviewed⁴. Our interest in the photochemical interactions between a sulphur linkage and an *ortho*-nitro group^{5,6} prompted an investigation of the photochemical chlorination of aromatic disulphides bearing an *ortho*-nitro substituent.

When a stream of dry chlorine was passed into a suspension of bis(2-nitrophenyl) disulphide (Ia) in carbon tetrachloride, while the suspension being irradiated with a Philips HPK 125W mercury-quartz lamp in a Hanovia photochemical reactor, the disulphide gradually went into solution. The reaction was complete in 30 minutes and work-up under anhydrous conditions afforded 2-nitrobenzenesulphenyl chloride (IIa). Similar reaction of bis(2,4-dinitrophenyl) disulphide (Ib) and bis(4-nitrophenyl) disulphide (Ic) afforded 2,4-dinitrobenzenesulphenyl chloride (IIb) and 4-nitrobenzenesulphenyl chloride (IIc) respectively. Bis(3-nitrophenyl) disulphide (Id) under these conditions gave no sulphenyl chloride, but only decomposed resinuous products which could not be characterised.

- I
a. $R_1 = \text{NO}_2$; $R_2 = \text{H}$; $R_3 = \text{H}$
b. $R_1 = \text{NO}_2$; $R_2 = \text{H}$; $R_3 = \text{NO}_2$
c. $R_1 = \text{H}$; $R_2 = \text{H}$; $R_3 = \text{NO}_2$
d. $R_1 = \text{H}$; $R_2 = \text{NO}_2$; $R_3 = \text{H}$
- II
a. $R_1 = \text{NO}_2$; $R_2 = R_3 = \text{H}$
b. $R_1 = R_3 = \text{NO}_2$; $R_2 = \text{H}$
c. $R_3 = \text{NO}_2$; $R_1 = R_2 = \text{H}$

The ease of chlorination of aromatic disulphides containing *o*- and *p*-nitro substituents can be ascribed to the favoured formation of *o*-nitrophenyl thiyl and *p*-nitrophenyl thiyl radicals. The formation of these radicals and hence the homolysis of the disulphide linkage is favoured due to the resonance interaction involving the nitro group at *o*- and *p*-positions (canonical forms III & IV).

Recent investigation by one of these authors⁶ has shown that *o*-nitrobenzenesulphenyl chloride undergoes an internal photo-redox reaction in aqueous acetic acid forming 2-aminobenzenesulphonic acid (Va). Therefore it was thought of interest to carry out the photolytic chlorination of the disulphides in aqueous acetic acid. Thus, bis(2-nitrophenyl) disulphide (Ia) and bis(2,4-dinitrophenyl) disulphide (Ib) on photolytic chlorination in aqueous acetic acid yielded 2-aminobenzenesulphonic acid (Va) and 4-nitro-2-aminobenzenesulphonic acid (Vb) respectively. Bis(4-nitrophenyl) disulphide (Ic) under these conditions afforded 4-nitrobenzenesulphonic acid (VI).

The formation of the 2-aminobenzenesulphonic acids is evidently through the intermediacy of the 2-nitrobenzenesulphenyl chlorides. This then follows the reported internal photo-redox reaction to form the 2-amino compounds. This view is supported by the non-formation of the amino compound in the case of the 4-nitro compound (Ic) in which the interaction involving the neighbouring nitro group is impossible.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Irradiations were carried out with a Philips HPK 125W high-pressure mercury-quartz lamp in a Hanovia one litre photochemical reactor. The lamp was surrounded by cylindrical water-jacket made of quartz which in turn was surrounded by a jacket containing the solution to be irradiated.

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Preparation of disulphides (I): The nitrodisulphides (Table-1) were prepared by refluxing the corresponding nitrochlorobenzene (2 equivalents) with sodium disulphide (1 equivalents) in ethanol⁷.

TABLE—1

Disulphide	m.p., °C	Nitrogen per cent*
<i>Bis</i> (2-nitrophenyl disulphide(Ia))	197	9.6(9.9)
<i>Bis</i> (2, 4-dinitrophenyl) disulphide (Ib)	215	14.0(14.1)
<i>Bis</i> (4-nitrophenyl) disulphide(Ic)	135	9.8(9.9)
<i>Bis</i> (3-nitrophenyl) disulphide(Ic)	188	9.5(9.9)

*Calculated values in parantheses

Photolytic chlorination of the disulphides in CCl₄: Details of a typical reaction are as follows: *bis*(2-nitrophenyl) disulphide (Ia, 5g) was suspended in CCl₄ (500ml) in the photochemical reactor. A crystal of iodine was added to this and a stream of dry chlorine was passed into the suspension while the solution being irradiated with the mercury-quartz lamp. The disulphide gradually dissolved. After 30 minutes the resulting yellow solution was concentrated to 50ml by distillation of the solvent on a waterbath. The solution was cooled in ice, filtered the yellow needles (4.5g, 90 per cent) of 2-nitrobenzenesulphenyl chloride (IIa), m.p., 73°C (lit⁸, 73°); found: C, 38.1; H, 2.0; N, 7.7 per cent; Calcd. for: C₆H₄NO₂SCl: C, 38.1; H, 2.1; N, 7.9 per cent.

The other nitrobenzenesulphenyl chlorides were also prepared similarly.

TABLE—2

Sulphenyl chloride	m.p., °C	Percentages*		
		C	H	N
2-Nitrobenzenesulphenyl chloride (IIa)	73	38.1(38.1),	2(2.1),	7.7(7.9)
2, 4-dinitrobenzenesulphenyl chloride (IIIb)	97	30.5(30.8),	1.3(1.3),	11.7(12)
4-Nitrobenzenesulphenyl chloride (IIc)	158	37.8(38.1),	2.0(2.1),	7.6(7.9)

*Calculated values in parantheses

Photolytic chlorination in aqueous acetic acid: Ia (5g) was suspended in acetic acid (800ml) containing 50 ml of water in the photoreactor. A stream of dry chlorine was passed into the suspension while it being irradiated with the mercury-quartz lamp. The disulphide gradually dissolved and after about 10 hrs a crystalline precipitate began to appear. After 20 hrs of irradiation, the solvent was distilled off and the residue (3.7g, 75%) on crystallisation from hot waer afforded orthanilic acid or 2-aminobenzenesulphonic acid (Va) as colourless flakes. Similar reaction of Ib afforded 4-nitro-2-aminobenzenesulphonic acid (Vb) in 65 per cent yield. Ic under these cenditions yielded 4-nitrobenzenesulphonic acid (VI), m.p., 197°; Found: C, 42.2; H, 2.8; N, 8.3%; Calcd. for C₆H₅NO₂S: C, 42.6; H, 2.9; N, 8.3%. The same compound (VI) was obtained on treatment of 4-nitrobenzenesulphenyl chloride with aqueous acetic acid.

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